

Terms of Reference of the European Essential Ocean Variables Network (ToR EOVS)

European EOVS

Communities of Practice Forum

The European Essential Ocean Variables (EOVS) Communities of Practice Forum (EOVS CoPF) facilitates coordination and collaboration among projects by developing and enhancing physical, biogeochemical, and biology and ecosystems EOVS governed by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) in support of global assessments.

1. Aim and Objectives

The Forum provides a collaborative platform for members to share and exchange information and to implement joint or coordinated activities that maximise impact and support the successful delivery of each of the projects' objectives. The Forum aims to:

- Facilitate further development and implementation of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVS) and of key ocean monitoring indicators, in compliance with international programmes and initiatives that support global assessments;
- Support further improvement to Earth System Models (ESMs) by promoting better use of EOVS data to represent key ocean processes across all domains;
- Enable better understanding of links between ocean physical, biogeochemical and biodiversity variability over time, and the impacts of environmental stressors;
- Strengthen the development of common, agreed standards for climate and biodiversity records content, format, quality and validation methodology;
- Work towards the interoperability of interdisciplinary data;
- Enable evidence-based decision-making and sustained European leadership in the ocean-climate-biodiversity science nexus by addressing key knowledge gaps identified by regional and global assessments.

2. Value proposition of the Forum

This Forum shall strive to bring added value to its individual members by providing:

- Access to shared relevant technical and scientific information across Forum members
- Maximised impact of Forum member activities through coordinated and co-organised communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, including stakeholder engagement;
- Optimised stakeholder engagement strategy oriented towards maximising impact while reducing stakeholder fatigue;
- Optimised use of budgetary resources to convene meetings and workshops focused on issues of common interest;
- A common voice and point of contact in representing Europe's leadership in further development and implementation of the EOVS framework in the EU and globally.

3. Membership

3.1 Founding members

The initial members and co-leads of the Forum are:

- [ObsSea4Clim](#) is represented by its coordinating organisation, the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI).
- [BioEcoOcean](#) is represented by its coordinating organisation, Uppsala University.
- [BioGeoSea](#) is represented by its coordinating organisation, GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel.

which have been funded under the call [HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 Closing the research gaps on Essential Ocean Variables \(EOVs\) in support of global assessments](#), and the [HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-02-2 - Closing the research gaps on Essential Biogeochemical Ocean Variables \(EOVs\) in support of global assessments](#), and are referred to as "sister projects".

3.2 Representation

Members of the Forum are represented by the projects/initiatives coordinating organisations, and other interested member project partners.

3.3 Joining the Forum as a member

The following initiatives and projects can join the Forum:

- EC-funded or co-funded projects with aims aligned with the Forum's ToRs,
- Other EU and non-EU initiatives which are actively contributing to the implementation of the GOOS EOVS framework.

These may join the Forum by submitting an expression of interest to the Forum Facilitator and upon the agreement of existing members.

3.3 Tasks

The Forum's members commit to collaborating on activities that align with its aims and objectives and to dedicating time to them accordingly.

3.4 Withdrawal and Termination from membership

Members may withdraw from the Forum at any time by written notification to the facilitator.

As projects conclude their activities, the organisations will automatically cease to be members of the Forum, unless otherwise indicated.

4. Forum Facilitator

The EuroGOOS Office acts as a Forum facilitator under the umbrella of [EOOS Framework](#). The Facilitator serves as a single point of contact for entities seeking to engage with the Forum and its members collectively, as well as for prospective projects and initiatives interested in joining the Forum.

The Facilitator tracks the progress of Forum activities.

The Forum Facilitator maintains a list of Forum members and their contact details.

Products, tools and other outcomes of the Forum and its activities may be utilised by the Forum Facilitator in the EOOS Framework, if relevant, according to the needs, capacity and agreement of members. This will ensure valuable outcomes remain available and accessible to the oceanographic community as a sustainable legacy of the Forum and its members.

5. Governance, Structure and Decision Making

The Forum is an informal cluster of projects and initiatives, and as such, it has no legal entity or formal decision-making authority.

5.1 Governance

The Forum is co-led by the ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean projects until their completion.

5.2. Decision making

Any decisions relating to its work and activities are made by its members on their own basis according to their own internal protocols.

5.3 Working Groups

Members of the Forum may form ad hoc working groups to address specific topics, activities or events. Such groups are temporary and composed of relevant individual experts from project partner organisations or other relevant initiatives.

6. Activities

The Forum facilitates a range of activities such as (non-exhaustive list):

- Common or coordinated stakeholder mapping and engagement for specific topic;
- Co-organisation of joint events (including clustering events), briefings, and other communication activities;
- Periodic joint meetings between HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 and HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-02-2 project's Steering Committees to exchange information, advice and updates;
- Issuing joint policy briefs and other publications providing a synthesis of outcomes and recommendations stemming from individual projects and initiatives;
- Invitation of HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 and HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-02-2 project's representatives to others' General Assemblies to share updates with all project partners;
- A joint application to the Horizon Results Booster with projects funded under the calls HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-8 and HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-02-2;
- Activities for developing multi-disciplinary ocean observing and recommendations for coordinated observing plans, contributing to the implementation of the EOOS Strategy 2023-2027.

7. Entry into force, lifetime and legacy

The Forum is established by the agreement of these Terms of Reference by its initial members ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean.

These Terms of Reference come into force when they are agreed by the initial members.

The Forum may be disbanded and cease to exist at any time by agreement of its members.

The Forum will cease to exist at the completion of all projects constituting its members, where no planned handovers are in place.

8. Resources

The European EOV Communities of Practice Forum has no resources or funds of its own. It relies on in-kind contributions by its members, supported by their members' funds or other resources (e.g. funds from the participating projects).

9. Revision of the Terms of Reference

These Terms of Reference may be revised at any time by agreement of its members.

10. Contact

Contact to the European EOV Communities of Practice Forum is via the Forum facilitator:

Name: EuroGOOS

Email: eov.forum@eurogoos.eu